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THE IMPORTANCE OF USING THE HEAT ENERGY OF THE EARTH

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the importance of using low-potential heat of the earth throughout the world. The dependence of the Earth's temperature on the geothermal gradient is given, and several options for heating and cooling systems for buildings using low-potential earth heat are considered.

Keywords: low-potential heat, geothermal, heat pumps, underground water.

Currently, one of the promising directions of energy supply is the use of heat pump systems that use the everywhere available heat source - the soil of the surface layers of the earth.

Two types of thermal energy of the earth can be distinguished - high potential and low potential. The first is a source of hydrothermal resources - that is, water heated to a high temperature as a result of geological processes. However, the use of high-potential heat of the earth is limited to certain geological regions. For example, in Russia, Kamchatka and the Caucasus are mineral water regions, while in Europe there are hot springs in Hungary, Iceland, and France.

Unlike hydrothermal resources, the low-potential heat of the earth can be used practically everywhere - through heat pumps. Heating of low potential heat of the earth, hot water supply, air conditioning (cooling), heating of roads in winter, prevention of icing, heating of fields in open stadiums, etc. can be used in various types of buildings and constructions.

Heat pumps in European countries mainly work in heating mode. In the US, heat pumps are often used in air-heating systems combined with ventilation, which allow both heating and cooling of the outdoor air. Usually, heat pumps are used in water heating systems. Since the efficiency of heat pumps increases as the temperature difference between the evaporator and the condenser decreases, underfloor heating systems with a

temperature of 35-40 °C are often used to heat buildings[1].

Geothermal heat pumps (GHP) represent nowadays the fastest growing segment of geothermal energy utilization. Central to this technology is the heat pump (HP) which can raise (or lower) the temperature of a working fluid. Therefore, GHPs can be used for heating and/or cooling. In moderate climate they can be operated as monovalent systems. In the great majority of cases the HP is driven by electric power[2].

In the last ten years, the number of systems that use the low potential heat of the earth to provide heat and cold to buildings has increased significantly. The largest number of such systems are used in the United States. In addition, they operate in Canada, Austria, Germany, Sweden, and Switzerland. Only private objects were built in Russia and Bulgaria. As a low-potential source of heat energy for the evaporators of heat pumps, the soil heat of the surface layers of the earth, as well as the heat of the exhaust ventilation air, are used here. The unit for hot water preparation is located in the basement of the building.

It includes the following main elements:

- steam compressive heat pump installations (HPI);
- hot water batteries;
- soil down potential heat energy and to be taken ventilation of the air down potential heat collect systems;

- circulation pumps, control and measurement equipment.

Down potential heat collect system main heat substitute element of the building perimeter according to from the outside is located coaxial type vertical soil heat substitutes to be is found. This heat substitutes of the house next to is located each 32 to 35 meters before 8 deep wells. Of the earth heat and to be released of air heat used by heat of pumps work mode stable and hot water consumption variable because of the hot water system battery with tanks equipped It includes the following main elements:

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water consumption variable because of the hot water system battery with tanks equipped.

Down potential heat of energy eye as relative in a way down a place with temperature under waters or of the earth surface layers the soil to use will be The heat content of the soil massif is generally high. The thermal regime of the soil in the surface layers of the earth is formed under the influence of two main factors - solar radiation falling on the surface of the earth and radiogenic heat flux from the subsoil. Seasonal and diurnal changes in the intensity of solar radiation and external temperature cause fluctuations in the temperature of the upper layers of the soil. The penetration depth of daily fluctuations of external air temperature and the intensity of incoming solar radiation depending on specific soil and climatic conditions vary from several tens of centimeters to one and a half meters. The depth of penetration of seasonal fluctuations of external air temperature and the intensity of incoming solar radiation, as a rule, does not exceed 15-20 m.

The temperature regime of the soil layers located below this depth is formed under the influence of thermal energy from the subsoil and practically does not depend on seasonal, or even more so, daily changes of external climate parameters. With increasing depth, the ground temperature increases according to the geothermal gradient, that is, it is about 3 °C for every 100 m (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dependence of ground temperature on geothermal gradient

The amount of radiogenic heat flux from the subsurface varies from place to place. For Central Europe, this value is 0.05 - 0.12 W/m².

Connects underground heat exchangers and heat pump equipment to the soil massif. In addition to "releasing" heat from the ground, underground heat exchangers can also be used to store heat (or cold) in the groundmass. In general, two types of systems for using the low-potential thermal energy of the Earth can be distinguished:

- open systems: underground water supplied directly to heat pumps is used as a source of low-potential thermal energy;
- closed systems: heat exchangers are located in the soil massif; through them, during the circulation of the heat carrier with a low temperature relative to the

ground, heat energy is "picked up" from the soil and transferred to the evaporator of the heat pump.

A key part of open systems are wells that allow groundwater to be extracted from soil aquifers and returned to those aquifers. Usually, paired wells are installed for this. The advantage of open systems is the ability to obtain large amounts of thermal energy at relatively low costs. However, such wells require maintenance. In addition, the use of these systems is not possible everywhere.

Basic requirements for soil and groundwater:

- sufficient water permeability of the soil, which allows replenishment with water reserves;
- good chemical composition of groundwater, which prevents problems related to the formation of sediments and corrosion on the pipe walls.

Open systems are often used to heat or cool large buildings. The world's largest geothermal heat pump system uses groundwater as a source of low-potential heat energy. It is located in Louisville, USA, and is used to provide heat and cold for a hotel-office complex; its capacity is about 10 MW. Sometimes systems that use the heat of the earth include systems that use the low potential heat of natural and artificial open water bodies.

Modeling of heat and mass transfer processes involved in the formation of the thermal regime of a multi-component system requires taking into account and mathematical description of various mechanisms of their implementation: heat conduction in individual

particles, heat transfer from one particle to another during their contact, molecular heat conduction in the medium filling the spaces between particles, steam convection, and humidity in the pore space and others.

Extraction of heat from the ground depends on the thermal conductivity of the soil; the thermal conductivity of the heat exchanger; the heat exchange surface area; the heat capacity and weight of the refrigerant and the velocity of the refrigerant in the heat exchanger.

To develop a methodology for calculating heat transfer processes in ground heat exchangers, a simulation research facility was created in the laboratory of the Department of Engineering Thermophysics (Figure 2), which allows simulating the operating conditions of a U-shaped ground heat exchanger.

1 - water tank, 2 - measuring tank, 3 - valves, 4 - U-shaped vertical ground heat exchanger, 5 - ground, 6 - housing, 7 - temperature sensors, 8 - flow meter

Figure 2 - Schematic diagram of the experimental stand for the study of heat transfer processes in soil heat exchangers

Experiments were carried out at the research facility and calculations were made confirming the best thermophysical parameters of moistened soil. Regularities of temperature distribution in the vicinity of the U-shaped ground heat exchanger are experimentally determined [3-4].

Thus, enough experience has been accumulated in the world, and several versions of systems for providing heat and cold to buildings using the lower potential heat of the earth have been created. These systems are a reliable source of energy that can be used for a long time and everywhere.

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